

A BRIDGE MADE OF DECOMMISSIONED WIND TURBINE BLADE: CONCEPTUAL DESIGN, EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS AND SITE IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the example of reusing wind turbine blade as a footbridge main girder. The design, numerical simulations as well as static and fatigue tests with the use of a distributed fibre optic sensors to assess the behaviour of the structure under load are described. Successful examination in the laboratory led to the first Polish implementation of a footbridge made of reused wind turbine blades. The main conclusions from this project and plans of the research team for future development of hybrid wind turbine blade - concrete bridge girder are also presented in the paper.

KEYWORDS

Wind Turbine Blade, DFOS, Bridge, FRP

INTRODUCTION

In 2021 about 6000 turbines were decommissioned worldwide due to the expiration of 20 years of service (Knight S., 2021). Currently 3800 composite blades are removed annually in Europe (Mishnasevsky L., 2021), but already in 2023 about 14000 blades are envisaged to remove and recycle (Wind Europe, 2019). The annual composite wastes are expected to grow about 12% per year until around 2026, and then 41% per year until 2034, reaching 28.1 million tonnes of blade material (Mishnaevsky L., 2021). Based on a predicted moderate growth scenario from the Global Wind Energy Council for future global wind power installations, a total of 16.8 million tonnes of composite materials will need to be decommissioned by 2030 and 39.8 million tonnes by 2050 (Bank LC., et al., 2017). According to (Liu P., et al., 2017), a total of 43 million tons of blade waste will be accumulated worldwide by 2050, 25% of them in Europe. Considering market growth scenario, the annual decommissioning of wind turbine blades is expected to reach 2 million tonnes by 2050. Structural recycling is a promising alternative end-of-life (EoL) solution for composite wind turbine blades. The process reuses the blades as large parts or construction elements. Structural recycling of blades prolongs the material lifetime, preserves the structural integrity of the composite, and needs relatively little reprocessing effort (Bank LC., et al., 2019), (Beauson J., et al., 2016), (Jensen JP., et al., 2018). When decommissioned, blades may still have enough residual capacity to be structurally recycled. In the study (Sayer F., et al., 2009) the effect of service life on wind turbine blades was investigated by comparing the actual state and performance of blades after 20 years to the design properties of the blades. The visual inspection and the full scale blade tests (including the moisture content, the natural frequencies, the coupling joints) revealed that no significant damage was found as well as no significant loss in blade stiffness. In structural recycling of wind turbine blades two options are often distinguished: reuse and repurpose. Reuse recycling assumes the refurbishment of decommissioned wind turbine blades, which mostly are still usable after their service life. It is the most desirable recycling option, however, it is very rarely possible to reuse a blade again due to the blade's condition. Several repurpose methods are under development in many ongoing research projects to involve decommissioned blades for civil engineering applications that benefit from the structural properties of the blades, such as: urban furniture (playground, bus shelters, public seating, signpost, etc) (Superuse Studios, 2014), affordable housing (roof, door and window frames and

elevated foundations) (Bank L., et al., 2018), (Eilers H., 2020) and bridges. Repurposed in this way, as a component of cheap house or bridge wind turbine blades can contribute in poverty alleviation. The last field of wind turbine blades repurposing is the main subject of the current R&D project carried out by the authors at the Rzeszow University of Technology (RUT), Poland. The main goal of the project was to develop and demonstrate a footbridge made of decommissioned wind turbine blades, suited for pedestrian and bicycle traffic, mostly in countryside applications. This paper describes the concept of the new footbridge system and presents the initial research results on its structural behaviour. Based on the output of this research the first Polish footbridge made of decommissioned wind turbine blades was built in 2021.

Figure 1. The concept of a footbridge made of a decommissioned wind turbine blades in Szprotawa, Poland

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

The concept of a footbridge assumes that its superstructure consists of at least one appropriately adapted (shortened) and edgewise oriented wind turbine blade, constituting the main girder of the structure, to which steel or timber transverse ribs are attached, supporting timber planks or FRP composite deck (Brückenspanne Deutsche Patentanmeldung DE, 2020). In the case when longer girder must consist of two blades, they are connected in root sections by means of a flange connection and bolts. In the support areas the FRP superstructure has concrete crossbeams, in which the ends of the blades are embedded. Concrete crossbeams with a thickness of 0.6-0.8 m are reinforced with steel or GFRP rebars, which are also used to connect the blades to concrete. The footbridge is equipped with standard balustrades, pavement and cornices. Depending on the required service width and load bearing capacity of the structure, the developed series of footbridges may include a relevant number of one- or two-part blade girders with the deck placed above or at the mid-depth of the girders. In the first footbridge of this concept, which was to build in Szprotawa, Poland, two-part blade girder was applied with steel transverse ribs in the form of truss adapted to the shape of the blade, and the timber planks were used for the deck placed at the mid-depth of the girders (Fig. 1). The theoretical span of the footbridge's superstructure is 16.4 m, the total length (with two tails) is 23.0 m and the service widths are 1.15 m and 1.20 m on both sides of the blade girder.

The developed series of footbridges was designed for LM 29.1 type wind turbine blades produced by the Danish company LM Wind Power. The proposed superstructure concept was checked according to the relevant Eurocodes. The value of the girder's self-weight was established according to blade's geometrical inventory and material testing results taking into account the actual FRP composite structure. The variable actions applied in design included the uniformly distributed load $q_{rk}=5.0$ kN/m² for pedestrian traffic and the wind load acting perpendicular to the girder. The static analysis was performed using the detailed finite-element (FE) model of the composite blade structure, which based on inventory and test results described in section 3 below. For code checking of the blade girder the final draft of the CEN Technical Specification for design of fibre-polymer composite structures was applied (FprCEN/TS 19101, 2022).

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Type and geometry of blade

The single LM 29.1 wind turbine blade has a total length of about 30 m, and its edgewise oriented depth varies from 1120 mm to 2365 mm. The footbridge girder is a fragment of a blade of the

designed length, formed after cutting off the tip and the root of the blade. The dimensions of the blade and its particular cross-sections were determined on the basis of laser scanning. The detailed inventory results in the selected cross-sections of the L29.1 wind turbine blade are presented in Fig. 2 and Table 1.

Figure 2. Characteristic cross-sections of the LM 29.1 wind turbine blade

Table 1: Cross-section' dimensions and the laminates' thicknesses of the LM 29.1 wind turbine blade

Section	External dimensions [mm]						Laminate's thickness [mm]						
	A	B	C	D	E	K	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	L	M
1						1685						85	
2						1680						25	38
3	1700	1670	395	560	600		25	28	32	20	21		
4	1870	1563	375	590	580		25	28	30	24	33		
5	2140	1355	365	590	610		30	30	30	20	31		
6	2340	1190	365	590	560		30	30	29	20	27		
7	2365	1075	365	610	600		32	32	26	15	25		
8	2310	965	365	605	610		32	33	25	15	25		
9	2255	860	367	610	610		30	33	25	15	25		
10	2195	767	370	630	630		30	30	20	15	33		
11	2142	685	370	630	630		30	30	25	15	25		
12	2085	605	370	650	650		30	30	22	15	23		
13	2025	538	375	650	650		30	30	22	15	23		
14	1960	485	370	635	630		30	30	21	15	23		
15	1895	445	370	620	620		30	30	20	15	22		
16	1825	410	370	620	620		30	30	20	13	22		
17	1763	376	370	615	615		30	30	17	13	22		
18	1710	357	370	620	640		34	35	10	11	20		
19	1642	320	370	630	635		31	35	10	12	23		
20	1570	295	375	620	625		31	30	10	----	25		
21	1500	276	365	620	630		32	31	10	----	22		
22	1430	260	360	635	680		25	25	10	----	22		
23	1355	240	360	635	640		30	32	10	----	21		
24	1280	232	380	----	----		40	37	10	10	23		
25	1200	217	225	----	----		35	30	10	20	22		
26	1120	205	220	----	----		35	27	10	17	8		

The LM 29.1 wind turbine blade is made of E-glass fibres and an epoxy resin matrix. Cross sections along the wind blade have three major subcomponents: the shell (the skin, which defines the airfoil shape), the spar cap (the primary load-carrying component), and the internal webs (the supporting component against shear and buckling). The shell and the webs are made of sandwich composites,

whereas the shear cap is made of solid composites. In this case the leading edge of the air foil is also made of solid composites.

Material testing

For material testing one entire LM 29.1 blade was divided and cut into 16 parts with a length of approximately 1.0 m each, from which specimens were taken for tests. Since the majority of the wind blade's composite is contained in the spar caps and shell panels, they are considered as the main components in the wind blade used in this study. The shear webs, comprising mostly of foam core, were not tested at this time. Specimens were taken from the spar cap and shell (both solid and sandwich composites) located mostly on the suction side of the blade.

The set of ASTM standards was used for material testing of blade composites (ASTM D3039 / D3039M, ASTM D3410 / D3410M, ASTM D3518/D3518M). The ASTM test methods determine the in-plane properties of polymer matrix composite materials reinforced by high-modulus fibres. The composite material forms are limited to continuous-fibre or discontinuous-fibre reinforced composites for which the elastic properties are specially orthotropic with respect to the test direction. It should be also noted that ASTM standards are intended for flat and thin composite specimens; however, the current work deals with thick and curved shell and spar cap specimens.

Strengths, elastic moduli and Poisson's coefficients of the composites extracted from the shell and spar cap along the blade are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Cross-section' dimensions and the laminates' thicknesses of the LM 29.1 wind turbine blade (together with figure 2)

Laminate	A	B		C		D			
Location	leading edge	shell		spar cap		shell			
Type	solid	sandwich skin		solid		sandwich skin			
Side		outer	inner			outer		inner	
Sample line	1 ()	2a ()	2b ()	3 ()	4 (+)	5a ()	6a (+)	5b ()	6b (+)
Tensile strength X_t [MPa]	221.57	77.39	73.55	464.25	-----	76.09	-----	100.80	-----
Young modulus E_x [GPa]	20.43	8.71	7.53	29.21	-----	8.65	-----	9.44	-----
Poisson's coeff. ν_{xy} [-]	0.34	0.34	0.45	0.32	-----	0.44	-----	0.55	-----
Compressive strength X_c [MPa]	275.43	228.14	145.87	368.46	-----	117.09	-----	100.60	-----
Tensile strength Y_t [MPa]	-----	-----	-----	-----	67.88	-----	128.12	-----	111.06
Young modulus E_y [GPa]	-----	-----	-----	-----	8.44	-----	8.77	-----	8.30
Poisson's coeff. ν_{yx} [-]	-----	-----	-----	-----	0.29	-----	0.33	-----	0.54
Compressive strength Y_c [MPa]	-----	-----	-----	-----	253.13	-----	159.98	-----	159.56
Shear strength S_{xy} [MPa]	-----	38.69	36.78	-----	33.94	38.05	48.67	50.40	39.45
Kirchoff modulus G_{xy} [GPa]	-----	3.06	2.75	-----	3.51	3.00	3.23	3.25	2.66

Full-scale structural testing

Two full-scale blade sections with a total length of 11.6 m were prepared for structural testing. The both sections were cut out of the two entire actual blades of LM 29.1 type (Fig. 3). The first blade's

cutting plane was located in the immediate vicinity of the blade root, while the second cutting plane was located at a distance of 11.6 m from the first cutting plane. Each blade section was oriented edgewise in accordance with the conceptual design of the footbridge such that the trailing edge of the blade was at the bottom, the leading edge at the soffit, internal webs were kept horizontal and the chord axis vertical.

Figure 3. The section of the blade for testing

The girders had a variable depth from 1685 mm (section 1) to 2365 mm (section 7). In the support zones of the girders, holes for reinforcing bars were made, connecting the body of the blade with the support crossbeams. The concrete crossbeams were made of concrete class C30/37 with dimensions 2,0 x 2,21 m x 0,6 / 1,2 x 2,21 x 0,6 m and were reinforced with 16 mm bars made of B500 SP steel (Fig. 4). In addition, a 10 mm thick steel plates were installed on the bottom of the crossbeams in order to properly support the girders on the bearings of the test stand. The plates were mounted in such a way as to obtain a theoretical span of the tested girders of 11.0 m.

Figure 4. The girder crossbeam: a) steel reinforcement; b) concrete crossbeam with bottom steel sheet

Two full-scale models were prepared in the same way to carry out the full test programme: one of them was used for static test and the other for fatigue test (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Two ready full-scale models for testing

Test set-up and instrumentation

Static test of the girder was carried out in a four-point bending scheme using two hydraulic actuators with a maximum force of 625 kN each (Fig. 6). The axial spacing of the actuators was 2.0 m.

Figure 6. Scheme of the test set-up

In order to correctly transfer the load from the hydraulic actuators to the girder, two steel load distribution elements with a width of 600 mm were prepared, placed in relevant spacing and glued to the composite girder's body with epoxy glue. The testing model was supported on two steel bearings: sliding and non-sliding. At the same stand and in the same test set-up fatigue test was also carried out (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. The full-scale model ready for testing

During static test, displacements of the girder and composite strains were measured at characteristic points and cross-sections. A total of 60 measuring sensors were used to assess the behaviour of the girder under static load (Fig.9 a, b). Vertical deflection was recorded using 18 Linear Variable Differential Transformers (LVDTs) placed at the bottom and the soffit of the girder. Four dial devices controlled the supports movement. The composite strains were measured using 38 foil strain gauges with a measuring base from 10 mm to 30 mm. All measurement data was collected using the HBM spider acquisition system with the QuantumX amplifier kit. All measurements were recorded at a sampling frequency of 2 Hz.

In addition, the distributed fibre optic sensors (DFOS) were used for continuous measurements of strains in composites at the length and depth of the girder. The DFOS system was provided to control strain and displacement measurement, further used in the structural health monitoring of the prototype footbridge. The DFOS system is characterized by the following features: accurate, reliable and distributed strain measurements, possibility of assessing shape and displacements, detection of local damages, reliable protection of the sensors, no need for surface installations, high durability, measurements from the real zero state of the structural element. The effectiveness of DFOS technique was evaluated through scaled laboratory experiments on a smart composite deck panel to be implemented in the next FRP composite bridges developed at RUT.

A total of ten DFOS sensors were used for strain measurement (Fig. 9 c). The single-mode telecom-grade optical fibres were applied and 10 mm virtual measurement sections spaced every 10 mm along optical fibres. The optical backscatter reflectometer (OBR) Luna 4600 based on linear Rayleigh scattering was used for distributed strain measurement. The OBR has a spatial resolution as fine as 10 μm and no dead zone.

Figure 8. The test instrumentation arrangement: a) LVDTs and dial gauges; b) foil strain gauges; c) distributed fibre optic sensors;

Testing programme

In order to develop the testing program, a numerical model of the tested girder was used, which was prepared in the same way as the numerical model used for designing the footbridge. The FE model geometry and its material parameters were based on the inventory and test results provided in chapter 3. In FE analysis the load during the static test was assumed as distributed on the actual contact surface between the blade body and the steel elements under actuators (model does not include steel elements).

Testing of the girder was carried out in 5 stages (Table 3). The test loads in the individual stages were determined as corresponding to the mid-span bending moments according to footbridge design for the following structure characteristics: span length $L = 17.0$ m, service width $B = 2.5$ m. These characteristics seem to be the most common for the future footbridge implementation and test results and conclusions for these characteristics can be easily extrapolated to the upper limit of the footbridge length range (22.0 m) and the lower limit of the footbridge width range (1.0 m).

Table 3. Girder's testing programme

Test stage	Footbridge design load	Mid-span bending moment [kNm]	Corresponding test load [kN]
I	characteristic combination of permanent and pedestrian loads	668.3	$2 \times 148.5 = 297.0$
II	fatigue load corresponding to max. deflection $L/300$ for $L=11.0$ m	756.3	$2 \times 168.1 = 336.2$
III	design (factored) combination of permanent and pedestrian loads	902.2	$2 \times 200.5 = 401.0$
IV	maximum load with LVDT measurement (~ twice as stage IV)		$2 \times 400.0 = 800.0$
V	maximum load at testing stand		$2 \times 625.0 = 1250.0$

Test results

The maximum girder's deflections at the load level corresponding to the characteristic and design (factored) bending moment for relevant load combinations were 13.72 mm and 18.90 mm, respectively. Especially the first value, which is about 1/800 of the girder length shows a very high stiffness of the girder, significantly higher than required for FRP footbridges.

Figure 9 shows the load-displacement plots for bottom (PD) and soffit (PG) zones under the load level twice greater than the maximum design load for the footbridge. The girder demonstrated linear-elastic behaviour until the applied total load reached 800 kN. The residual displacement observed after

reloading in the last stage was negligible. For the sake of comparison , two plots at three sections were presented: for the point located in the bottom zone (PD6) and for the corresponding point located on the soffit zone (PG6). The deflections' difference at the peak load is only 1.7 mm, i.e. 0.10% of the minimum girder depth and it revealed that the body deformation of the blade under high load was insignificant.

Figure 9. Load – displacement plots for bottom (PD) and soffit (PG) zones

The maximum strains that occurred at the bottom and soffit zones in mid-section are far less than the ultimate strain of relevant FRP composites. The maximum longitudinal strain in the bottom zone obtained in the vicinity of the mid-section at the load corresponding to the design bending moment was 1972×10^{-6} , which is far less than the ultimate strain obtained from the material tests. Moreover, the maximum strain at this location for the maximum load $2P = 1260 \text{ kN}$ was only 36% of the ultimate strain of the bottom zone laminates. The strains in the soffit zone were on average almost 30% less than the bottom ones. The highest compressive strain (-1519×10^{-6}) was only 11.3% of the ultimate compression strain and it is the highest utilization level of blade composites obtained for design bending moment. The utilization of the soffit zone for the maximum load was only 37% and is almost the same as for the bottom zone.

Figure 10. Strains distributed along the optic fibre S4 in the subsequent stages

The exemplary results of DFOS strain measurement are presented hereafter, showing the main advantages of the novel strain measurement method. Strain distribution measured by the selected optical fibre in the subsequent load stages is presented in Fig. 10, which show strain profiles in the bottom zone of the girder recorded by the optical fibre S4. The values measured at the maximum load of 1260 kN just before the end of the test are highlighted in red. The strain profiles clearly showed

that not only the global response of the girder, but also local effects could be observed, what is impossible to capture when using conventional spot measurement. The plots perfectly identify the initiation moment (i.e. the corresponding load) and location of shell' delamination. The moment of initiation (peak on the strain profile) was captured neither by means of visual observation of the girder under loading nor spot strain measurement. Although a loud sound was heard indicating the beginning of the delamination process, visual observation did not allow to locate this failure, nor to assess the extent of its propagation. Both of these very important information the point of view of SHM could be obtained by observing a distributed measurement of strains along the length of the S4 optical fibre. The location and visual assessment of the delamination could only be performed under a much higher load, when the failure of the laminate took the form (crack) threatening the collapse of the girder.

Distributed strain measurement can also change the conventional way of analysing structural elements, extending the analysis from one domain (time) to two domains (time and length). Thus, the results can be presented on spatial visualizations (Fig. 11). The strain profiles for the girder are characterized by a great variety and large gradients along even small length. This is a perfect example of the limitations of conventional spot strain gauges, which average strains along the base in one point of the element. Even the small change in the spot gauge location causes the significant change in the measured values and thus the results interpretation. That is why it should be performed with the special caution and precision. Distributed strain sensing completely eliminates this problem, showing the full and comprehensive picture of the structural behaviour.

Figure 11. The full-scale model ready for testing

Figure 12. Local failure of the bottom zone

Under maximum load of 1260 kN, the girder exhibited no global destruction. However, the girder suffered the severe local damage at the final load stage. During it, there was a loud sound that was attributed to local delamination of bottom laminate in the girder' shell. The visual examination of the bottom zone of the girder after unloading revealed the about 150 mm long two-sided crack at the mid-span section (Fig. 12). A thorough analysis of the plots from the DFOS sensors showed that the crack occurred at a load of 1050 kN, which could be considered as a ultimate capacity of the girder. Figure

13 shows also the location of a conventional strain gauge (in the immediate vicinity of crack), whose readings did not indicate any disturbance in the distribution of strains under increasing load.

However, during the full loading range the girder behaved linearly until the maximum load of 1260 kN was applied and no residual displacements were observed after unloading. It revealed that the detected local failure of FRP shell had no influence on the global structural behaviour of the girder. The strain analysis showed that the strain fields, induced in the shell under the maximum load, were far below the ultimate strength of blade's composites. Therefore, the main reason of local failure seems to be the manufacturing flaw, introduced to the shell during laminates production, or the damage caused during the long exploitation of the blade in wind turbine (e.g. bird impact). The fatigue test started in the four-point bending scheme at fatigue load $\Delta P = 2 \times 168.1 = 336.2$ kN. Under this fatigue loading the girder survived 927,913 load cycles. After reaching this number of cycles, one steel element distributing the load on the girder was destroyed. The inspection of the girder after the completion of the first phase of the fatigue test did not show any local failure of the girder. Since it was not possible to continue the fatigue test with two actuators, it was decided to continue the test under the same total load ($\Delta P = 336.2$ kN) generated by one actuator in a 3-point bending scheme. The girder survived additional 19,041 cycles, resulting in a total of 946,954 fatigue load cycles. This time, the girder was locally damaged in the soffit zone, in the immediate vicinity of the steel distributing element (Fig. 13). Local failure in the form of a laminate crack with a length of about 1.5 m was caused by a twofold increase in local fatigue load distributed directly in the mid-section of the girder. The laminate in the soffit zone of the girder (the leading edge) cracked parallel to its longitudinal axis, and the crack was discovered directly under the steel element (0.5 m) and about 1.0 m outside it toward one of supports.

Figure 13. Crack of the soffit laminate

SITE IMPLEMENTATION

The results of the experimental investigation were used to design and analyse the superstructure, as well as, to develop the details, specifications, and construction methods needed for the footbridge constructed in Szprotawa, Poland in 2021.

The main load-bearing element of the footbridge is a girder made of two sections of composite wind turbine blades, connected in the middle of the span by means of a bolted flange connection. Both girder elements were cut from two typical composite blades with a length of about 25 m and variable height in the range from 1.685 m (blade hub) to 2.365 m. The girder elements were created after cutting off the nose (end) of the blade, and their total length is 10.65 m. Steel flanges were used to connect both parts of the girder, in which the hubs of typical composite wind turbine blades are equipped. After connecting both elements, the girder has a total length of approx. 21.3 m. 11 lattice crossbars, 3.94 m wide (max.) and 0.48 m high, made of mutually welded square steel pipes, were fastened to the lower part of the girder along its entire length. The crossbars were connected to the laminates of the girders with bolts, and the laminates in the connection zones were additionally reinforced with steel sheets. In order to strengthen the support zones, the pairs of end crossbars were braced with internal bracing, and a steel grate made of I-beams was additionally attached to the bottom.

Prior to transportation to the site and installation in the field, the superstructure was constructed in full-size in the Anmet’s factory in order fine tune the assembly process. After the composite blades were properly cut to the designed size, a steel structure of the platform (crossbars, stringers, grate) was attached to each element with bolts, which had previously been manufactured and protected against corrosion in the factory. After connecting both parts of the span on the assembly site, it was moved in its entirety by means of a light crane over the supports and supported on bearings (Fig. 14a). Before opening for public use (Fig. 14b), the footbridge was subjected to a series of static and dynamic proof loading tests. Concerning the field performance, the novel blade bridge system fully conformed to the requirements of relevant standards and recommendations. As the blade bridge girder is a prototype solution, the structural health monitoring (SHM) system based on distributed fibre optic sensors (DFOS) was designed, implemented and calibrated under the proof load of the completed footbridge. SHM results are believed to help further evaluation the service life and durability of such footbridges under public use and environmental impact. Creep deformation of the blade girder will also be studied at this time.

a) Installation of the footbridge span

b) The footbridge in service

Figure 14. Installation of the footbridge span

CONCLUSION

This paper presents the selected results of research on a decommissioned wind turbine blades for use in bridge construction. The results were compared to the design assumptions and the performance criteria formulated in the footbridge design as well as to other FRP bridge girders available on the market. The results of the research were used to design of the world's first footbridge made of decommissioned wind turbine blades built in Szprotawa, Poland.

The research were performed within the R&D project: “An alternative to the utilization of older generation wind turbine blade (WTB). The use of composite WTB for the bridge construction, Poland. This project was funded by the Stage I - sub-action 2.3.2 Innovation vouchers for MSP. Furniture research work on wind turbine blade for construction bridge will by performed within the LIDER13/0031/2022 funded by the National Centre for Research and Development, Poland, Warsaw, within the framework of the LIDER Program.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.